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*Social Capital and Loans Availability of Technological SMEs:
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ABSTRACT

This paper investigated some SMEs in Shenzhen Stock Exchange and some non-listed technology-based SMEs and analyzed the impact of two types of social capital on the availability of loans, then compared their differences from the perspective of three-stage innovation. It was found that: (1) The more technological innovation activities, the more difficult it is for enterprises to obtain bank loans; on the whole, relational capital and structural capital can all effectively promote the acquisition of loans. (2) The positive effects of two types of social capital on the availability of loans are best reflected in the transforming stage of innovative achievements, the effect of patent output stage is moderate, but not effective in the stage of R&D investment. In-depth comparison found that in the environment of less R&D investment, more number of granted patents and larger proportion of new product output value, the two types of social capital can play a more effective role. (3) In the short term, relational capital can replace structural capital, especially in the stage of more patents and larger proportion of new products' output value.

INTRODUCTION

Social capital is an important way for SMEs to obtain financial support, especially for technological SMEs. There are two main reasons: first, the innovation output of technology-based SMEs in China is full of uncertainty, and the market prospect is relatively bleak. Second, due to the imperfect credit system, there is information asymmetry between SMEs and commercial banks, which makes it difficult for SMEs to obtain loans scientifically and effectively. So, in order to make the information exchange between banks and enterprises more fully, the technological SMEs must be persuasive in all stages of innovation input, output and achievement transformation, and closely contact with banks, so as to improve the availability of loans.

In fact, compared with traditional enterprises, the role of social capital in technological SMEs is much more complex. The first is that the impact of social capital on bank loans is not the same in the three stages of innovation with different characteristics: R&D investment, patent output and achievement transformation of technological innovation. The second is that in the social network nodes of SMEs such as governments, banks, other enterprises, industry-university-research institutions and financing service institutions, due to the participation of innovation activities, there are different nodes, the functions of the department are different. This paper aims to clarify these two issues, in order to provide a theoretical reference for SMEs to obtain more effective bank loans in the process of technological innovation full of risks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This paper divides social capital into relational capital and structural capital, and mainly focuses on debt financing to sort out the relevant literature on the relationship between social capital and SMEs' financing.

Relational Capital

Relational capital is mainly formed by the right and position relationship of individuals who are familiar with each other. In debt financing of SMEs, it mainly comes from the relationship with the governments and banks. (1) Government relations. The governments' social capital of enterprises refers to the capability of enterprises to obtain scarce resources from the government by establishing ties with the governments. In the debt financing of SMEs, the relationship between governments and enterprises has played a positive role, such as reducing loan difficulty (Li et al., 2008)^[12], obtaining longer repayment period, paying lower loan cost (Charumilind et al., 2006)^[5], and loosening guarantee requirements (Jiang, 2009)^[9]. (2) Bank relations. The banks' social capital of enterprises mainly comes from the long-term cooperative relationship established between banks and enterprises. The relevant research focuses on the relationship loan, and achieves the purpose of financing by solving the information asymmetry problems such as opaque information, high financial risk and insufficient collateral (Petersen and Rajan, 1994; Berlin and Mester, 1998)^{[14][3]}. Bank-enterprise relationship can effectively reduce the cost of bank search, negotiation, supervision, use of collateral, and sharing loan projects (Boot, 2000)^[4].

Structural Capital

As La Porta (1997)^[11] said, the social network relationship in western society is mainly the social trust relationship between strangers. In this paper, the social capital formed by such relationships is called structural capital. SMEs in China are more dependent on relational capital, because in the familiar network, the motivation of members to default is weak, otherwise it is easy to be kicked out of the network. Practice shows that other enterprises (Beatriz and Christian, 2000)^[2], scientific research institutes (Ballesteros and Rico, 2001)^[1] and intermediary service agencies (Diamond, 1984)^[7] also play an active role in enterprise financing.

To sum up, social capital evaluation indicators can be roughly divided into two categories, one is the level of personal relationship, the other is the level of organizational or institutional relationship, respectively corresponding to the relationship capital and structural capital divided in this paper. On the whole, the two types of social capital all have positive roles in promoting the financing of SMEs.

Review

The space for further study is as follows: first, considering the different contribution of different indicators of social capital to corporate financing, we should consider separating relational capital and structural capital from the whole social capital. On the basis of classification, the paper compares the role of two types of social capital in SMEs' financing. Second, we can carry out comparative study from different stages of technological innovation according to the unique characteristics of technological innovation behavior of science and technology enterprises. Based on this, this paper attempts to divide the social capital into two categories according to the relationship attribute, and compare and analyze the difference of their role in obtaining bank loans in the three stages of technological SMEs' innovation.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Data Sources

The data of technological innovation in this paper comes from CSMAR database, and the data of social network relationship comes from intermediary investigation institutions. Financial enterprises, ST and PT enterprises, abnormal data situation, merger, reorganization and transfer of control right are excluded. A total of 419 valid samples were obtained, of which 302 were listed companies on the SME Board of Shenzhen Stock Exchange. The data section is 2018.

Variable Setting and Measurement Method

(1) Explained variables. The explained variable is loan availability. The enterprises surveyed in this paper have loan demand and pay attention to whether they have obtained loans. Referring to Kano et al. (2011)^[10], this variable is set as a binary variable of 0-1, i.e. the tested enterprise obtains a loan and is assigned a value of 1; otherwise, it is assigned a value of 0.

(2) Explanatory variables. ① Social capital (SC). It includes relational capital (SRC) and structural capital (SSC), which are measured by Coefficient Variation Method. ② Technological innovation. The research and development investment (R&D), the number of authorized patents (Lngpt) and the proportion of new product output value (Invpro) are selected to measure the level of enterprise innovation. These three sub variables reflect the logical relationship of the three stages of innovation. Because some enterprises do not participate in the innovation activities of a certain stage or the whole process of innovation, the technological innovation variables may have the phenomenon of right skewness. In order to solve this problem, add 1 to the three sub variables, and then take logarithm (Rossi, 2005)^[14].

(3) Control variables. This paper selects three kinds of control variables. ① Basic information variable. It includes Age, Industry, Ownership and Employees. ② Financial variables. It includes production scale (Property), gross profit (Gprofit), growth capacity (Growth), profitability (profit) and debt level (DebtR). ③ Other variables. It includes Loyalty and Brand.

Empirical analysis

The Effects of Social Capital and Technological Innovation on Loan Availability

This paper constructs a classification evaluation model to analyze the relationship between two types of social capital, third-stage innovation sub variables and bank loan availability.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Logit}(\text{Loan}) = & \alpha + \beta_1 \text{SRC} + \beta_2 \text{SSC} \\ & + \gamma_1 \ln(1 + R \& D) + \gamma_2 \ln(1 + \text{Lngpt}) + \gamma_3 \ln(1 + \text{Invpro}) \\ & + \sum \lambda X + \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), α is a constant term, β_1 , and β_2 is the coefficient of relational capital and structural capital respectively, γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_3 is the coefficient of R&D investment, number of authorized patents and proportion of new product output value respectively, λ and X is the coefficient and symbol of series of control variables respectively, ε is the error item.

First of all, in SPSS 20.0, we did a correlation test on the explanatory variables in model (1), and found that there was no multicollinearity among the explanatory variables. The regression results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Effect of Social Capital and Technological Innovation on Loan Availability

	Loan
Intercept	0.388** (0.517)
SRC	0.516*** (0.654)
SSC	0.109* (0.732)
$\text{Ln}(1+R\&D)$	-0.589*** (-1.115)
$\text{Ln}(1+\text{Lnapt})$	-0.117* (0.378)
$\text{Ln}(1+\text{Inpro})$	-0.130 (0.452)
Age	-0.217* (-0.084)
Observation	419
LR	36.771***

Note: *, **, *** denotes statistical significance at the level of 10%, 5% and 1% respectively, and the standard error is shown in the brackets. The regression results of control variables were omitted. The same below.

Analysis of Explanatory Variables

(1) Both types of social capital have significant positive effects on loan availability. Among them, the significance level of relational capital is significantly higher than that of structural capital, which indicates that the positive role of relational capital in obtaining bank loans for technology-based SMEs is far stronger than that of structural capital. This reflects such a reality: in the current social network relationship of SMEs, the network relationship dominated by government-enterprise relationship and

bank-enterprise relationship has a strong capability to obtain bank loan resources for SMEs, followed by regional trust, while the role of structural network relationship between SMEs and other enterprises, universities, scientific research institutes and intermediary agencies is relatively weak.

(2) In terms of the three stages of innovation, the R&D investment, the number of authorized patents, the proportion of new product output value and the availability of loans are all negatively correlated, which indicates that the more innovation activities of small and medium-sized technology-based enterprises are, the less favorable it is to obtain bank loans. This is consistent with Czarnitzki and Kraft (2004)^[6], Hyytinen and Pajarinen (2005)^[8], among which the significant level of R&D investment and authorized patents is 0.01 and 0.10 respectively. The proportion of new product output value is not significant, which shows that the inhibitory effect of technological innovation on loan availability becomes weaker and weaker with the shift of value chain in the three stages of innovation. In the stage of R&D investment, small and medium-sized technology-based enterprises are the most difficult to obtain loans, because the uncertainty in this stage is too large, and banks generally dare not take risks in lending. When entering the stage of authorized patent, the inhibition of loan availability is not too strong, because the patent output of enterprises in this stage is the basis of achievement transformation, and the uncertainty of market prospect is less. In the stage of achievement transformation, although the availability of loans has not been significantly inhibited, the proportion of new product output value does not reflect the effectiveness, which shows that even after the transformation of innovation achievements, banks still have not changed their attitude to actively support technology-based SMEs.

A Comparison of the Effect of Two Types of Social Capital on Loan Availability

In order to deeply understand the difference of the effect of two types of social capital on loan availability in the three stages of innovation, this paper divides the three innovation sub variables into two groups. Namely, R&D, Lngpt, Invpro is corresponding to divided into group A and group B, group C and group D, group E and group F respectively. The grouping criteria is as follows: taking the median as the boundary, those greater than the median are classified into groups A, C and E, and those less than the median were classified into group B, D and F. The innovation variables in model (1) are deleted and revised to model (2).

$$\text{Logit}(\text{Loan}) = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{SRC} + \beta_2 \text{SSC} + \sum \lambda X + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

The meanings of variables and symbols in equation (2) are the same as those in equation (1). The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Effect of Two Types of Social Capital on Loan Availability

	Loan					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
Intercept	0.303* (0.556)	0.367* (0.630)	0.245** (0.473)	0.183* (0.601)	0.487* (0.434)	0.169* (0.459)
SRC	0.199 (0.720)	0.540** (0.533)	0.235*** (0.598)	0.310* (0.502)	0.681*** (0.841)	0.304** (0.500)
SSC	0.057 (0.831)	0.321 (0.675)	0.163* (0.717)	0.186 (0.798)	0.101* (0.952)	0.077 (1.334)
Observation	155	264	197	222	162	257
LR	38.104***	40.262***	37.870***	41.551***	40.195***	37.275***

Note: The results of control variables in this table and the following table are omitted.

(1) Relational capital. In group A, the relational capital and loan availability is not significantly positively correlated, which indicates that in the innovation environment with large R&D investment, the greater the innovation risk of small and medium-sized technology-based enterprises is, at this time, relational capital stock can not effectively promote the acquisition of loans. But in group B, the situation is much better, and the R&D investment and loan availability is significantly positively correlated at the level of 0.05, indicating that the innovation with large R&D investment, the innovation risk of technological SMEs is higher. In the environment of moderate innovation risk, relational capital can offset the risk and effectively promote the acquisition of loans. In group C and

group D, the relational capital has a significant positive impact on loan availability at the level of 0.01 and 0.10 respectively, which indicates that with more patent output, the larger the relational capital is, the more favorable it is to promote loan acquisition. While the patent output is less, the role of relational capital is greatly weakened, but it is still effective. The financing results of this stage will help enterprises to further realize the transformation of innovation achievements. In the stage of achievement transformation, relational capital has a significant positive correlation with loan availability at the level of 0.01 in group E, which indicates that when innovation achievement have a good application effect in the market, relational capital can promote the acquisition of loan. In group F, relational capital can still positively affect the loan results, but its effectiveness is weakened.

(2) Structural capital. Structural capital has no significant effect on the loan availability, which indicates that the stock of structural capital has no value in the process of obtaining loans for small and medium-sized technology-based enterprises, or its role has been restrained for some reasons. Only in group C and group E, the structural capital has a positive effect on loan availability at a lower level of significance, which indicates that the structural capital can play a positive role only with better innovation output and transformation effect.

The Substitution Effect of Two Kinds of Social Capital

In order to further understand whether the role of two types of social capital in obtaining bank loans in the three stages of innovation of technology-based SMEs is substitutable, this paper sets up a sub model with cross multiplication to test it, as shown in equation (3)

$$Loan = \alpha + \beta_1 SRC + \beta_2 SSC * SRC + \beta_3 SSC * (1 - SRC) + \gamma C + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) reflects the substitution relationship between relational capital and structural capital. Among them, the $SSC * SRC$, $SSC * (1 - SRC)$ are multiplicative terms. By simply calculating and comparing the coefficients of the cross multiplication terms, we can judge the substitution effect of social sub capital.

If the relational capital stock of the tested enterprise is small, that is, $SRC = 0$, then equation (3) changes as follows:

$$Loan = \alpha + \beta_3 SSC + \gamma C + \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

If the relational capital stock is large, i.e. $SRC = 1$, then equation (3) is transformed into:

$$Loan = \alpha + \beta_1 + \beta_2 SSC + \gamma C + \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

If equation (4) is equal to equation (5), then β_2 is less than β_3 , which indicates that the impact of structural capital on loan availability is weaker. Its theoretical meaning is, in the process of obtaining bank loans, enterprises with larger relational capital stock are less dependent on structural capital than enterprises with small relational capital stock.

Then, after testing the correlation of the explanatory variables of the above sub models, the forced regression was carried out, and the results were sorted out as shown in Table 3

Table 3: Substitution Effect of Two Types of Capital on Loan Availability

	Loan					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
<i>SRC</i>	0.278* (0.144)	0.201** (0.048)	0.362*** (0.035)	0.299* (0.019)	0.711*** (0.343)	0.430** (0.396)
<i>SSC*SRC</i>	0.080 (0.467)	0.165 (0.530)	0.124* (0.172)	0.251 (0.150)	0.388 (0.418)	0.213 (0.457)
<i>SSC*(1-SRC)</i>	0.097 (0.693)	0.107* (0.525)	0.267** (0.222)	0.118 (0.107)	0.215** (0.339)	0.249* (0.310)

Note: For brevity, intercept and LR values are omitted in this table.

Table 3 shows that the significance level of SRC is significantly higher than that of SSC*SRC, and the coefficient is also larger than the latter. In the regression results of SSC*SRC, except for group C, they are not significant. This fully shows that when the relational capital stock of small and medium-sized technology-based enterprises is large, they will hardly rely on structural capital in the process of obtaining bank loans. In addition, the significance of SSC*(1 - SRC) is stronger than that of SSC*SRC on the whole, which indicates that when the relational capital stock is small, the larger structural capital stock can promote loan acquisition to a certain extent, especially in the achievement transformation stage.

Relational capital has the most effective effect on the technology-based SMEs to obtain bank loans, and has the highest contribution. It has substitution effect on structural capital, and the substitution effect is most obvious in group C and group E.

CONCLUSION AND ENLIGHTENMENT

This paper discusses the impact of two types of social capital on the loan availability of technology-based SMEs and their differences in the three stages of innovation. The main conclusions are as follows: first, the more innovative activities, the more difficult it is to obtain loans, especially in the stage of R&D investment. Second, the more the stock of the two types of social capital, the easier it is to obtain loans. Among them, relational capital plays the more important role, followed by structural capital. Third, when the R&D investment is large, the two types of social capital have no obvious effects on the loan availability, while when the number of authorized patents and the output value of new products account for a large proportion, the positive effect is stronger. Fourth, relational capital can replace structural capital. Policy implications are as follows:

(1) Prudent investment in R&D. Although independent innovation is a strong determinant of enterprises, SMEs should be based on reality, objectively evaluate the value of participating in R&D, invest in R&D, participate in technical cooperation and absorb spillover knowledge. (2) Build up the stock of structural capital. The value of structural capital has the largest space to improve, which means that the development of structural embedded network relationship should be paid more attention to. In the long-term development planning of technology-based SMEs, the effect of structural capital will accumulate over time. We should strive to participate in enterprise alliance, industry-university-research alliance and other organizational forms to make up for their own shortcomings and enhance their innovation capability.

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